

SELECTED FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUBSIDISED PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL EDUCATION IN BURETI SUB- COUNTY, KERICHO COUNTY, KENYA

Joyce Chirchir¹,

Hellen Sang²,

Eric Mibei²

¹Postgraduate Education Student,
University of Kabianga, Kenya

²Dr., Lecturer, University of Kabianga, Kenya

Abstract:

In the last decade, the government of Kenya has emphasized the provision of education as a leading policy initiative. As a result, the government instituted the Free Primary Education (FPE) in the year 2003, which resulted in high enrolment of the pupils at the Primary level. However, costly school fees were found to be a major reason that the vast majority of primary graduates could not attend Secondary schools because their families could not afford the cost. The provision of Subsidized Secondary Education (SSE) is very important in Kenya given that the country is a low income one. SSE policy was launched in 2008 with an aim of ensuring that all primary pupils from class eight are able to continue well with secondary education. There are limited studies on the SSE programme currently and it is against this background that this study sought to shed more light on the programme. The purpose of this study was to establish factors influencing implementation of SSE policy on access and retention of education in public secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County. The study aimed at establishing the factors that influence effective implementation of free secondary education in public schools in Buret Sub-County, in Kericho County, Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population was the school Principals/Deputy Principals, Teachers, Sub-County Director of Education, District Quality Assurance and Standard Officer. Simple random, systematic and stratified sampling procedures were used. Both qualitative and quantitative data was collected from the study. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics after data cleaning and coding. Quantitative data was analyzed using frequency counts, means and percentages while qualitative data was

analyzed thematically. Results of data analysis were presented using frequency distribution tables, bar graphs and pie charts. SPSS program was used in the analysis. The findings show that the major challenges facing implementation of FSE includes; Delay in disbursing the SSE funds, over enrolment of students leading to strained physical facilities, inadequate facilities, lack of funds from the government for expansion, acute teacher shortage, poor cost sharing strategies. Key intervention measures for mitigating the identified challenges includes; Government to release funds in good time to avoid straining relations between suppliers and schools management, increasing bursaries support from M.O.E, NGOS, CDF for continuing students, providing clear policy on fund disbursement and increasing FSE allocation per student among others.

Keywords: subsidised public secondary school education; implementation; factors influencing; Kenya

1. Introduction

Education is widely seen as one of the most promising paths for individuals to realize better, more productive lives and as one of the primary drivers of national economic development UNESCO (2005). Education also forms the basic component upon which economic, social and political development of any nation is founded World Bank (2009). Investment in education can help foster economic growth, enhance productivity, contribute to national and social development and reduce social inequality. According to UNESCO (2005), the level of a country's education is one of the key indicators of its level of development. Globally, education is recognized as a basic human right.

The Human Rights Charter treats education as one of the human rights. Additionally, Bishop (2007) indicates that in 1948 the Universal Declaration of Human Rights laid down Article 26, that everyone had the right to education and that education would be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Education for all has been discussed in international forums, for example United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) World Conference at Jomtien, Thailand in 1990 and its follow up in Dakar, Senegal in 2000. Consequently, governments around the world have invested huge amounts of their expenditure on education. Before independence, education for most African countries was geared towards perpetuating and producing aims and content inherited from the pre-independent past. The current re-thinking however ensures that the African is rooted in the culture of his/her

environment and prepared for participation in nation building through educational reforms World Bank (2008).

Despite the tremendous increase in primary school access, secondary school access has remained low. In 2009, the secondary school net enrollment rate was approximately 50% (World Bank, 2009), while in 2010 the primary to secondary school transition rate was equally low at 55% MOE (2010). This shifted the focus towards universal secondary education with Uganda beginning the implementation process in February 2007 UNESCO (2008). The Kenyan government followed thereafter by introducing the idea of subsidizing tuition fees as per Sessional paper No. 1 2005 Shikanda 2008; Mibei (2010), so as to increase transition rates from primary to secondary schools to 79%; which according to the economic survey of 2008, stood at 59.9%.

The government of Kenya has invested heavily in education so as to achieve the education related Millennium Development Goals (MDG) and Vision 2030. However, financing of education has become more expensive Eshiwani (1993). The report on the Task Force on Affordable Secondary Education (2007) drew a conclusion that equity in provision of education had not been achieved since less than 4% of secondary students were drawn from the poorest per capita expenditure groups while 28.2% were from the richest quartile Republic of Kenya (2008). Secondary education in Kenya has grown tremendously Republic of Kenya (2008). In 1963, there were 151 secondary schools, a student population of 30,121. This has progressed over the years with the current students' population being 1,180,300 and the number of secondary schools being 6,485 Republic of Kenya (2008).

2. Statement of the Problem

Subsidized Secondary (SSE) policy was launched in 2008 with an aim of ensuring that all primary school pupils from class eight are able to continue with secondary education. Implementation of Subsidized Secondary Education in Kenya was a major step in expanding access to education to majority of students from poor background. This was further reinforced by the international agreement on Education for All World Bank (2008).

The government provided subsidies towards funding SSE, however there were other costs that were catered for by the parents. Concerns have however been raised over effective implementation of this programme, and the impact of SSE on quality and access of secondary education following structural factors including inadequate and delayed disbursement of subsidies to school, shortage of human resources, limited

physical and instructional resources Asayo (2009a). The study therefore examined the extent to which these factors influencing the implementation of free secondary education SSE in Bureti sub-county, Kericho County.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to establish the factors influencing the implementation of Subsidized Public Secondary education in Bureti sub-County, Kericho County.

2.2 Objectives

1. To investigate the availability of instructional materials and its influence on the implementation of SSE
2. To determine the availability of physical infrastructure and its influence on the implementation of SSE.

2.3 Research Questions

1. How does the availability or lack of instructional materials affect the implementation of SSE in Bureti Sub-County?
2. How physical infrastructure does affect the implementation of SSE in Bureti Sub-County?

2.4 Justification

The World Declaration and the Framework for Action UNESCO (1990) popularly known as the Jomtien Conference (1990) which urged Nations to intensify efforts to attain EFA and ensure basic learning needs are met, that is basic learning content required by human beings to be able to survive, to develop their capacities to participate fully in development, and to improve the quality of their lives.

Kenya considers education a right to every child and has formulated policies and initiated Programs within the education reforms agenda that an all-inclusive and equitable basic education. These interventions have been implemented over the years either through joint Kenya Education Sector support Program (KESSP) financing framework or through non pooled partners in different parts of the country.

Subsidized Secondary Education was meant to reduce disparities in education and ensure attainment of EFA. SSE however comes with enormous challenges (Daily Nation, 2008). This hampers the attainment of EFA and equity in education as well as violation of the right of the child. This study became very necessary to address the gap between policy and practice, plans and reality in the implementation of Subsidized Secondary Education. The contribution of SSE and other targeted interventions have

neither been comprehensively reviewed nor documented to establish their contribution towards inclusive and equitable basic education MTI (2009). The findings would help MOE to review and streamline Subsidized Secondary Education with the aim of narrowing or eliminating the gap.

3. Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Capital Theory of School Effectiveness and Improvement to find out the factors influencing implementation of Subsidized Public Secondary Education Programme in Bureti Sub-County, Kericho County. The applicability of the theory in the study can be seen in the fact that all theoretical concepts such as outcomes, leverage-intellectual capital, and social capital have a bearing on the quality of education each master concept is defined in terms of two subsidiary concepts and twelve specifically educational concepts are set within this framework to provide the theory. It is proposed that through a simplified model the range and fertility of the theory can be exemplified and tested in three specific cases, the changing nature of the school effectiveness and improvement in knowledge economies, citizenship education and teacher effectiveness. The proposed framework is a fruitful contribution to understanding of the chain of mechanism that creates school success and failure Hargreaves (2001).

The desired outcomes of SSE policy are provision of quality education to every Kenyan child who is a graduate from secondary school, regardless of gender, ethnic background or socioeconomic status. Based on Capital Theory of School Effectiveness and Improvement, effective schools mobilize their intellectual capital and social capital to achieve desired educational outcomes of intellectual capital and social capital to achieve desired educational outcomes and moral excellence Hargreaves (2001). For this to be achieved there is need for the government, school management, parents and the community to work together for the benefit of the schools. SSE in Kenya is an example of a partnership between the community and other stakeholders in provision of education. Using this theory, the study will seek to unearth the challenges that could hinder the desired outcomes and the creation of intellectual capital and social capital in public secondary schools.

4. Methodology

The study employed descriptive survey research design. The target population for this study consisted a sample of secondary schools in Bureti Sub-county, Kericho

County which has fifty (50) public secondary schools. Most experts suggest sample sizes of between 10-30% Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) Taking the upper limit of 30% against the accessible population of 50 gives a sample of 15 cases. Simple random sampling techniques was used to select 15 principals in public secondary schools and 100 teachers. To ensure fair representation of the study population, proportionate stratified sampling was used in selecting and distributing the 15 schools. The subject for study included a sample of 15 secondary school principals and 100 teachers from the schools. Others subject of study included 1 SCDE and 1 DQASO of Bureti Sub-County. Validity and reliability of instruments were ascertained. After the test-retest, the instruments attained a reliability coefficient of 0.70 using the Cronbach alpha coefficient which was considered high enough to continue with data collection.

The study was carried out in public secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County, Kericho County, Kenya.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

This section describes the biographic characteristics of respondents in the study area. Such description was important in providing a clear understanding of the respondents and institutions included in the study and which may have influenced the results based on the objectives of the study. The demographic characteristics covered in this section include; gender composition, teaching experience, length of stay in current station and length of service as principal and academic qualification of the principal.

The age distribution of the sampled Head teachers/Teachers is summarized in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Age of Head teachers and Teachers

Age	Head teachers		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
25-30years	-	-	20	20
31-40years	2	13	30	30
41-45years	5	33	35	35
Above 46 years	8	53	15	15
Total	15	100	100	100

The findings show that there were no head teachers in the age bracket of 25-30year while 20 (20%) of the teachers were in that age bracket, two 2 (13%) of the head teachers were in the age bracket of 31-40, while 5 (33%) aged between 41-45 and majority 8 (53%) aged above 46years. While for the teacher's majority, 65 (65%) were of middle age of 31-45years. From the above findings, it is a clear indication that age is factor as far as

leadership was concerned; those who were older had the position of being head teachers unlike for the case of teachers. These results were attributed to the fact that to be appointed a principal one must have served as a teacher, Head of Department and Deputy Principal for at least three years in each level.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Type	Head teachers		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Male	10	67	60	60
Female	5	33	40	40
Total	15	100	100	100

The findings in Table 2 indicate that there is gender disparity for both the head teachers and teachers. Ten (67%) of the head teachers and 60 (60%) of the teachers were male, while 5 (33%) of the head teachers and 40 (40%) of the teachers were female. The dominance of the male head teachers to female principals might be due to the fact that until the year 2002 the gender factor into positions of leadership was not taken into consideration. Consequently, most of the mixed schools in the Sub-County were headed by men. This made the proportion of male principals more compared to female principals.

Table 3: Type of school

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Girls boarding	29	29
Boys boarding	33	33
Mixed day	35	35
Mixed boarding	3	3
Total	100	100

Table 3 shows that majority of schools were mixed day schools 35 (35%), which was followed by boys boarding 33 (33%), girls boarding 29 (29%), mixed boarding 3 (3%). The pure boys and girls were the county schools which were meant to admit students from all over the county. The full day mixed schools were the newly established CDF funded schools which were started to cater for transition of the large number of students from the free primary education programme.

The study sought to establish the teaching experience of the teachers. The findings are presented in the table 4 below.

Table 4: Teaching Experience

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 2years	16	16
2-5years	21	21
6-10years	42	42
11-20years	13	13
Over 20years	8	8
Total	100	100

The findings show that majority 42 (42%) of the respondents have taught for between 6-10 years hence considered experienced. A considerable number of teachers 8 (8%) had taught for over 20 years hence considered very experienced, while 16 (16%) of the teachers have taught for less than 5 years hence considered inexperienced. The findings imply that there are few very experienced teachers in the sub-county who could adjust to changes easily and capable of handling SSE issues with ease. The finding of very few inexperienced teachers in the sampled schools was an indication that the government has employed very few teachers in the last five years. The government introduced SSE within this period of time which helped raise enrolment considerably with no corresponding increase in the number of teachers Adan (2008). According to the study, this scenario could have contributed to understaffing in public secondary schools in the sub-county which would undermine the successful implementation of SSE.

3.2 Availability of the instructional materials and physical infrastructure in secondary schools for the implementation of SSE

A. Physical infrastructure

The second objective aimed at establishing the availability of instructional materials and physical infrastructure in secondary schools for the implementation of free secondary education and to achieve this objective, the researcher asked the respondents to give their responses on the adequacy of both physical infrastructure and instructional resources. Availability and adequacy of physical facilities in secondary schools is essential if schools were to realize their goals and implement SSE. The inadequacy of these resources tends to compromise the quality of teaching and learning in schools. School resources including classrooms, desks, chairs, computers, textbooks and other instructional equipment/materials are critical in making teaching/learning more effective. They help to improve access and educational outcomes. The findings are shown below;

Table 5: Adequacy of physical infrastructure

	Very adequate		Adequate		Undecided		Inadequate		Very inadequate		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
	Classrooms	4	4	67	67	0	0	29	29	0	0	100
Laboratories	0	0	46	46	0	0	46	46	8	8	100	100
Library	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	58	42	42	100	100
Toilets	4	4	58	58	4	4	34	34	0	0s	100	100
Field space	8	8	33	33	4	4	50	50	4	4	99	99
Desks, chairs and lockers	4	4	75	75	0	0	21	21	0	0	100	100
Dining hall	33	33	21	21	4	4	13	13	29	29	100	100
Computer laboratories	4	4	33	33	0	0	33	33	29	29	100	100
Water	21	21	67	67	0	0	12	12	0	0	100	100

Table 5 shows that student desks, chairs, lockers, classroom, water, toilets and laboratories topped the list in terms of level of adequacy. Other responses are indicated in the same table. The facilities that were inadequate included; computer laboratory, library, field space, and dining hall. Availability and adequacy of physical facilities in secondary schools was essential if the schools were to realize their goals. The inadequacy of these resources tended to compromise the quality of teaching and learning in schools. These resources should be provided in quality, quantity and in time for effective teaching-learning process. The study by Muchiri (2012) found out that the physical facilities that were inadequate were classrooms and desks, which impacted negatively on the implementation of SSE.

The findings in Table 5 show that 67 (67%) indicated that classrooms were adequate 29 (29%) indicated inadequate. Provision of classrooms created an enabling environment for the learning teaching processes.

It was however established that none of the schools have adequate library which is a very important facility in quality education. Library is an essential factor in teaching-learning process. It forms one of the most important educational services. The educational process functions in a world of books.

The chief purpose of a school library is to make available to the pupil, at his easy convenience, all books, periodicals and other reproduced materials which are of interest and value to him but which are not provided or assigned to him as basic or supplementary textbooks Owoeye (2011).

Quite a number of the respondents 46 (46%) indicated that laboratories were adequate which was however the same as those who indicated the same as inadequate 46 (46%) while 8 (8%) said it was very inadequate. This is in agreement with the observations of

Ayodo (1989) who acknowledged that both the government and community have strengthened the capacity of schools in the provision of learning facilities. The findings in Table 5 show that the major outcomes in the implementation of FSE included strained laboratory facilities, lowering educational quality and standard.

On toilets, 62 (62%) indicated that they were adequate, while 34 (34%) indicated they were inadequate and 4% were undecided. This is in line with the study by Muchiri (2012) shows that latrines were adequate in most of the Kenyan schools.

41 (41%) of the schools have adequate field space compared to 54 (54%) of those with inadequate. Desks, chairs and lockers were found to be adequate in almost all 79 (79%) of the schools while only 21 (21%) indicated they were inadequate. Only 55 (55%) of the respondents agreed to have adequate dining hall, 42 (42%) have inadequate and 4 (4%) were undecided to answer.

Computer laboratories which are vital facility in secondary schools were found to be adequate in only 37 (37%) of the schools while majority 63 (63%) indicated inadequacy of the facility. Despite the importance of ICT in schools and the strategies developed by the government and other stakeholders, as formulated in Sessional Paper no. 1 of 2005, research has revealed that several schools were not implementing ICT to support teaching, learning and management in schools. Manduku *et al.*, (2010) observed that despite the benefits of ICT, the school management had not fully implemented the policies developed by Ministry of Education. Laaria (2013) assert that some schools had developed guidelines on how to implement ICT but no attempt was made to implement them.

The findings however found out that majority of the schools 89% had adequate water except for 11 (11%) which had inadequate. The schools without water supply were most likely to be the day schools.

Olembo and Cameroon (1986) indicated that school principals face increasing administrative difficulties. These include inadequate and badly constructed buildings; shortage of books, equipment, lack of proper school furniture particularly desks, poor or sometimes non-existent maintenance and repairs, over-crowded classrooms, poor infrastructure and few supporting services especially health services. Shortage of these resources could compromise the quality of secondary education in the country. For instance, inadequate classrooms would mean overcrowding and hence making the classroom environment unfavourable for learning.

B. Instructional facilities

The study sought to establish the availability and adequacy of instructional facilities. Instructional resources which are educational inputs are of vital importance to the

teaching of any subject in the school curriculum. The findings are summarized in the Table 6;

Table 6: Teachers responses on Instructional resources

Resources/ Material	Very adequate		Adequate		Undecided		Inadequate		Very inadequate		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
	Textbooks	4	4	25	25	0	0	54	54	17	17	100
Computers	4	4	21	21	4	4	54	54	17	17	100	100
Lab equipment /chemicals	0	0	42	42	0	0	50	50	8	8	100	100
Chalks/dusters	20	20	64	64	0	0	11	11	5	5	100	100
Teaching aids	0	0	29	29	8	8	50	50	13	13	100	100

The findings in Table 6 show that most of the schools 71 (71%) do not have adequate text books compared to only 29 (29%) who indicated that the text books were adequate. The findings concur with the study by Mobegi's (2007) in Gucha which revealed that textbooks, stationery, science equipment and teaching aids were either unavailable or inadequate.

Majority of the respondents 71 (71%) also indicted that computer facilities were inadequate while only 25 (25%) said they were adequate and 4 (4%) were undecided. This raises a lot of concern as the MOE has not given funding to schools for the purchase of the ICT through the FSE programme. However, the DQASO noted that some schools had received ICT materials through the MOE where the funding and equipping was fully done and others did not received. This was in agreement with the findings of KESSP Report (2005) that indicated that although computers were introduced in 1988, there was little emphasis on its use as an instructional strategy.

The findings in Table 4.10 show that for laboratory equipment and chemicals, 42 (42%) reported they were adequate while 58 (58%) said were inadequate. In general, the headteachers and teachers shared the view that laboratory equipment were inadequate. Though the SSE policy has contributed to increase provision of the teaching and learning resources in secondary schools as the government provides substantial amount of money towards resources, this has been strained by high enrolment in schools. Ochenje (2008) in her study also found out that provision of instructional materials was identified as one of the major achievements of FSE programme, particularly through reducing burden of education on parents.

According to Omega (2015), crucial facilities such as classroom, staffroom, library, laboratories, water supply, electricity, toilets and desks were inadequate in most schools implying they accounted for the poor performance in most schools.

Cumulative 84% of the teachers observed that chalks and duster were adequately available in their schools. Only a small percentage, cumulative 11 (11%) perceived their availability as inadequate and 5 (5%) of the teachers perceived very inadequate.

Teaching aids were also found to be adequate in only 29 (29%) of the schools, 63 (63%) indicated they were inadequate and 8 (8%) were undecided. Obonyo (1987) noted that instructional materials such as textbooks, visual and audio materials not only enhance communication between the teacher and the learner but also facilitates child-centred learning and learning through discovery.

Table 7: Head teacher’s response on adequacy of CDF support for development of facilities

Support	Adequate		Inadequate		No support		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Adequacy of CDF support	7	46.67	5	33.33	3	20	15	100

Figure 1: Adequacy of CDF support

The findings in Table 7 and Fig 1 shows that 7 (46.67%) sampled head teachers agreed that the support they get from CDF for development of facilities was adequate while 5 (33.33%) said it was inadequate and 3 (20%) said they do not get any support at all. This indicated that CDF support given to schools was inadequate to cater for the physical development of the facilities. These findings agree with the findings of Olembo *et al.*, (1992). His argument was that there is still very high percentage of children who belong to the school age group and were not receiving education mainly due to financial limitations of the African countries. It is therefore through this basis that we find the inadequacy of CDF support in Kenya has contributed to slow implementation of the SSE policy in public secondary schools within Bureti Sub-county.

The findings concur with the findings of Getange *et al.*, (2014) which reported that Constituency Development Funds (CDF) were inadequate to complement the free

day secondary education initiative. In addition, the results of this study agrees with Njeru and Orodho (2003) who argued that the national bursary allocation is insufficient as it caters about 10% of the fees owed by needy student per school. This shows that lack of enough bursary and CDF support has affected the implementation of FSE in secondary schools.

The study further sought to find out the extent to which the physical facilities affect space; the respondents were required to fill in the Likert table start the most to the least against the indicators, the findings are summarized in the table 4.12

Table 8: Head teachers’ response on the extent to which free secondary education affected space

	Large extent		Neutral		Minimal	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Classrooms	10	66.67	5	33.33	0	0
Laboratories	10	66.67	5	33.33	0	0
Toilets	5	33.33	10	66.67	0	0
Administration block	10	66.67	0	0	5	33.33
Dining hall	5	33.33	10	66.67	0	0
Kitchen	3	20	0	0	12	80

The findings in Table 8 show that head teachers responses on the extent to which free secondary education affected space showed 10 (66.67%) indicating that it affected classroom, laboratories and administration to a large extent while 5 (33.33%) were neutral. However, 3 (20%) said it affected kitchen and store to a large extent. This shows the need to address the issue of physical facilities with a view of improving these facilities. These results agreed with the Mackay (1981) and Kamunge (1988) reports which argued that physical infrastructures of education are in short supply and the government need to make concerted effort to meet administration, infrastructural and professional costs of education.

C. Observation Guide on Physical Facilities

The study sought to establish the condition of the physical facilities in school and the responses are provided in table 9. The observation guide was necessary in order to ascertain the responses of the principals concerning the various variables under investigation. It was expected that by obtaining an independent opinion to collaborate the principals’ responses the findings of the research are bound to be more reliable.

Table 9: Facilities Directly Related to Tuition

Facility	Condition	Percent (%)
Teachers tables	good	56.3
	fair	37.5
	bad	6.3
Teachers	good	46.7
	fair	46.7
	bad	6.7
Staffroom	good	31.3
	fair	56.3
	bad	12.5
Student chairs	good	18.8
	fair	75.0
	bad	6.3
Students desks	good	37.3
	fair	56.3
	bad	6.5
Classroom floor	good	37.5
	fair	56.3
	bad	6.3
Classroom walls	good	43.4
	fair	54.3
	bad	2.3
Lighting	good	46.7
	fair	33.3
	bad	20.0
Black board condition	good	75.0
	fair	18.8
	bad	6.3
Laboratories	good	57.1
	fair	42.9
	bad	0.0

Table 9 shows that majority of respondents indicated facilities directly related to tuition were either in good or fair condition. Except for lighting, none of the facility was rated as bad by 7% of respondents. The second objective aimed at establishing the availability of instructional matters and physical infrastructure in secondary schools for the implementation of free secondary education. The findings of the study show that classrooms were adequate in 71% of the schools studied and 29% reported that the

classrooms were inadequate. It was however established that none of the schools have adequate library which is a very important facility in quality education.

Library is an essential factor in teaching-learning process. It forms one of the most important educational services. The findings also indicate that laboratories were adequate in 46% of the school in Bureti sub-county. The schools in the region have enough toilets except for 38% of those who reported inadequacy.

Facilities like desks, chairs and lockers were found to be adequate in 79% of the schools while only 21% indicated they were inadequate. Dining hall was found adequate in relation to the number of the students in 55% the schools. This implies that that the enrolment is more than the required or the designated number of students. The findings however found out that majority of the schools 89% have adequate water except for 11% which have inadequate. The schools without water supply are most likely to be the day schools.

The findings on availability of physical and instructional resources found that 71% do not have adequate text books compared to only 29% who indicated that the text books were adequate. Majority of the respondents 71% also indicted that ICT facilities were inadequate while only 25% said they were adequate and 4% were undecided.

The study found that high cost of acquisition and maintenance of ICT equipment was a barrier that had continued to constrain adoption and integration of ICT in schools.

This was in line with existing literature; Farrell (2007), where he pointed out that the cost of ICT is unaffordable to many schools. Access to internet services for more utilization of computers in learning process was more expensive for many schools.

For laboratory equipment and chemicals, 42% reported they were adequate while 58% said were inadequate. Almost all 89% of the schools indicated the availability of chalks and dusters contra to only 11% with inadequate. Teaching aids were also found to be adequate in only 29% of the schools, 63% indicated they were inadequate and 8% were undecided. This study revealed that many instructional materials except ICT equipment necessary for the implementation of SSE policy in public secondary schools were adequate in Bureti Sub-county. These findings are in agreement to the findings of Ochenje (2008) that found out that provision of instructional materials was identified as one of the major achievements of FSE programme. Efforts should however be made to adequately avail ICT equipment as this is now on the ICT age.

4. Conclusion

1. Free secondary education increased enrolment which has caused overstretching of the available resources. The government has not budgeted for the extra students who enroll which also affected the proper implementation of the program.
2. Both physical facilities and instructional resources were inadequate in most of the schools. Some of the schools even lack some facilities which are vital for effective teaching and learning. The study found out that the physical facilities that were directly related to classroom teaching, such as ICT facilities and science laboratories, and libraries are inadequate. Inadequacy of playgrounds in most schools was probably due to acute shortage of land in the area.

4.1 Recommendations

1. There is dire need for the Government to review the Subsidized Secondary Education budget to take into account the varying enrolment in the course of the year and also the inflation factor, this will ensure that quality education is made available to all students through availability of required resources.
2. The Government should also take the responsibility of taking up the infrastructure and development of schools, and this could be achieved by reintroducing schools equipment schemes to make provision for textbooks and other learning materials. The textbook: pupil ratio should be maintained and improved.

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